

IMPACT OF FAMILY CLIMATE ON THE MENTAL HEALTH OF B.Ed. TEACHER-TRAINEES IN RELATION TO THEIR ACADEMIC STREAM

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to find out the effect of family climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees in relation to their academic stream. Descriptive survey method was used for this study. Sample consisting 160 B.Ed. teacher-trainees was selected by using random sampling technique from four B.Ed. colleges of Bareilly district. Family Climate Scale developed by Harpreet Bhatia & N.K. Chadha (2019) and Mental Health Inventory developed by C.D. Aagshe and R.D. Helode (2008) used for data collection. Data was analyzed using Mean, S.D. and ANOVA (F-test). Finding reveals that there was significant main effect of two dimensions of family climate i.e. expressiveness and organisation and significant interaction effect was found on expressiveness, conflict and organisation dimensions of family climate.

KEYWORDS: Family Climate, Mental Health, academic stream, B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

INTRODUCTION

Mental health is the ability to balance one's ambitions and objectives, to handle life's stressors, and to make psychosocial adjustments. A person who has a healthy mental state is motivated to lead a more fulfilling life. Mentally healthy person has a vibrant, purposeful attitude toward both himself and other people. It is a known truth that individuals with healthy mental states have positive attitudes toward their jobs and professions. Individuals with poor mental health, on the other hand, frequently struggle to feel comfortable performing the tasks related to their jobs or professions. This made it abundantly evident that a person's mental health was determined by their capacity to view themselves favourably, perceive reality, integrate their personalities, and have attitudes that are conducive to the welfare of their social groups.

A person who is mentally healthy may interact with their surroundings, family, and contribute to the development and enhancement of society (Lewkan, 1993). Humans must adjust to the world and to one another in order to be as successful and happy as possible. This is what is meant by mental health. It is the capacity to uphold civil behaviour, a cheerful attitude, composure under pressure, and perceptiveness (Meninger, 2004).

Family is the first social climate where individual fulfils his/her physical, mental and cultural needs. Family interaction plays an important role in the development of an individual. The healthy functioning of these interaction patterns enhances mental health. Thus we can say that family climate moulds the behaviour, personality, attitude, aptitude, self-esteem and mental health of an individual (Kaur *et al*, 2015). Webster dictionary (2004) defines 'family' as a group of persons,

consisting of parents and their children. It also defines 'climate or environment' as the aggregate of all external and internal conditions affecting the existence, growth and welfare of organisms.

Education streams as a branch or sub branch of a field of study. The broad four streams are after class x for students to select-Science, Commerce, Humanities/Arts and Vocational. Science stream is related to Medical studies and Engineering with subjects like Physics, Chemistry, Biology and Mathematics. Commerce stream is related to trade, commerce, business and financial marketing. Humanities/Arts are the widest of all, and are related to education in subjects like History, Geography, Political Science, Psychology, Sociology, Languages and Anthropology etc. Vocational stream is related to professional courses such as Fashion Designing, Photography and Nursing etc.

Family climate plays an important role in every field of student's life. In this specific context the present research will undertaken to specifically provide empirical answers of these questions like what is role of family climate on mental health of science, commerce and humanities/arts stream of B.Ed. teacher-trainees. A study was conducted on mental health of secondary school students in relation to family climate by Sing and Devi (2018). Findings of this study revealed that there found a significant positive relationship of mental health with family climate. Similarly, Shivanae (2011) reported significant difference of family climate and mental health of tribal and urban secondary school students. But it was found that no study has been conducted effect of family climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher trainees in relation to education stream. Hence the researcher has decided to undertake, the study of effect of

family climate on mental health of science, commerce and humanities/arts stream B.Ed. teacher trainees.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To explore the effect of different dimension of family climate on mental health of science, commerce and humanities/arts stream B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
2. To detect the interaction effect of different dimensions of family climate and education stream on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

1. There is no significant effect of different dimensions of family climate on mental health of science, commerce and humanities/arts B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
2. There is no interaction effect of different dimensions of family climate and education stream on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

RESEARCH DESIGN & METHODOLOGY

The researcher used descriptive survey method. Population of the present study consists of all the teacher-trainees of B.Ed. colleges affiliated to M.J.P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly. Sample of 160 teacher-trainees of 4 B.Ed. colleges of Bareilly district selected with the help of simple random sampling techniques. **Family Climate Scale (FCS)** developed by Harpreet Bhatia & N.K.Chadha(2019) and **Mental Health Inventory (MHI)** developed by C.D. Aagshe and R.D. Helode (2008) were used for the study. Data were analysed using Mean, S.D., and F-test (ANOVA).

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant effect of different dimension of family climate on mental health of arts, commerce and science stream B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Table 1.1: Descriptive statistics of mental health of arts, commerce and science stream B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Dimensions of Family Climate	Family climate Group	Stream	N	Mean	S.D.
1.COHESION	High FC	A	8	23.38	4.241
		C	2	24.50	9.192
		S	10	22.10	3.957
	Average FC	A	40	22.28	3.508
		C	10	23.30	2.908
		S	61	22.13	3.918
	Low FC	A	15	20.00	2.726
		C	1	24.00	0
		S	13	19.69	4.191
2.EXPRESSIVENESS	High FC	A	21	21.33	2.763
		C	0	0	0
		S	20	22.25	3.492
	Average FC	A	39	21.92	3.841
		C	11	23.91	3.910
		S	61	21.61	4.248
	Low FC	A	3	25.00	4.359
		C	2	21.50	0.707
		S	3	21.33	2.887
3.CONFLICT	High FC	A	2	27.50	0.707
		C	2	24.50	9.192
		S	5	24.20	4.550
	Average FC	A	43	21.84	3.477
		C	7	23.00	2.828
		S	66	22.00	4.061
	Low FC	A	18	21.33	3.515
		C	4	24.00	2.944
		S	13	19.54	2.665
4. Acceptance and Caring	High FC	A	5	23.80	4.868
		C	0	0	0
		S	3	24.00	6.928
	Average FC	A	39	21.56	3.567
		C	9	23.78	4.410
		S	64	22.05	3.802

5.Independence	Low FC	A	19	22.00	3.215	
		C	4	23.00	1.414	
		S	17	20.24	4.116	
	High FC	High FC	A	2	27.50	0.707
			C	2	20.50	3.536
			S	3	25.33	2.517
		Average FC	A	21	22.62	4.031
			C	6	24.83	3.869
			S	40	22.30	4.268
Low FC	A	40	21.20	3.073		
	C	5	23.20	3.421		
	S	41	20.95	3.667		
6.Active-Recreational Orientation	High FC	A	10	25.60	3.340	
		C	3	21.33	3.055	
		S	22	23.73	3.494	
	Average FC	A	37	21.22	3.400	
		C	8	24.38	3.462	
		S	47	21.11	4.082	
	Low FC	A	16	21.06	2.645	
		C	2	23.50	6.364	
		S	15	20.87	3.758	
7 .organization	High FC	A	28	21.89	4.193	
		C	4	23.00	5.598	
		S	27	21.78	3.896	
	Average FC	A	17	22.35	2.644	
		C	4	25.75	2.630	
		S	33	22.64	3.782	
	Low FC	A	18	21.39	3.363	
		C	5	22.20	2.168	
		S	24	20.50	4.283	
8. control	High FC	A	7	23.86	5.367	
		C	4	21.25	2.500	
		S	11	24.09	2.914	
	Average FC	A	32	21.47	3.016	
		C	7	25.14	4.059	
		S	42	22.24	4.310	
	Low FC	A	24	21.83	3.608	
		C	2	22.50	2.121	
		S	31	20.26	3.425	

Two Way ANOVA has been performed for testing the hypothesis-1. The result of ANOVA for mental health have been shown in table-1.2

Table 1.2 summary of ANOVA (Effect of different dimensions family climate on mental-health of arts, commerce, science stream B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Dimension	Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean squares	F-Ratio	Result
Cohesion	Stream	36.574	2	18.287	1.288	N.S.
Expressiveness	Stream	11.982	2	5.991	3.407	Significant
Conflict	Stream	43.453	2	21.726	1.550	N.S.
Acceptance and caring	Stream	38.977	2	19.488	1.344	N.S.
Independence	Stream	9.027	2	4.513	0.326	N.S.
Active recreational orientation	Stream	21.257	2	10.629	0.808	N.S.
Organization	Stream	45.068	2	22.534	4.556	Significant
Control	Stream	5.290	2	2.645	0.193	N.S.

The above table 1.2 shows that f value for main effect on two dimensions i.e. expressiveness and organisation is 3.407 and 4.556 respectively which was significant and for other dimensions like cohesion, conflict, acceptance & caring, independence, active recreational orientation and control main effect was found to be non-significant. So the null hypothesis is rejected on the basis of expressiveness and organisation dimension of family climate and accepted on cohesion, conflict, acceptance & caring, independence, active recreational orientation and control dimensions of family climate with respect to education stream of B.Ed. teacher trainees. It can be concluded that mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees

influence on expressiveness and organisation dimensions of family climate with respect to education stream.

Hypothesis2: There is no significant interaction effect of different dimensions of family climate and education stream on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Two way ANOVA has been performed for testing the hypothesis-2. The result of ANOVA for mental health have been shown in table-2.1

Table 2.1 summary of ANOVA (Interaction effect of different dimensions of family climate and subject stream on mental-health B.Ed. teacher-trainees.)

Dimensions	Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean of squares	F-Ratio	Result
1.	Cohesion*stream	13.353	4	3.338	0.235	N.S.
2.	Expressiveness *stream	49.932	3	16.644	3.132	Significant
3.	Conflict*stream	57.586	4	14.397	4.027	Significant
4.	Acceptance and Caring*stream	33.272	3	11.091	0.765	N.S.
5.	Independence *stream	84.308	4	21.077	1.524	N.S.
6.	Active-Recreational Orientation *stream	96.610	4	24.152	1.837	N.S.
7.	Organization *stream	17.173	4	4.293	4.296	Significant
8.	Control*stream	121.428	4	30.357	2.209	N.S.

The above table 2.1 reveals that f value interaction effect was found significant for dimensions expressiveness, conflict and organisation which is 3.132, 4.027 and 4.296 respectively and for other dimensions like cohesion, conflict, acceptance & caring, independence, active recreational orientation and control, interaction effect was found to be non-significant. So the null hypothesis is rejected on the basis of expressiveness and organisation dimension of family climate and accepted on cohesion, conflict, acceptance & caring, independence, active recreational orientation and control dimensions of family climate with respect to education stream of B.Ed. teacher trainees. It can be concluded that mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees influence on expressiveness and organisation dimensions of family climate with respect to education stream.

CONCLUSION

From above study it can be concluded that on expressiveness and organisation dimension family climate can affect mental health of B.Ed. teacher trainees. The mean score of Science stream trainees was found higher as compared to other streams. Science Students tends to be more logical and organised as compared to Arts and Commerce stream. So they enjoy better mental health as compare to their counterparts..

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